

Anatomical Factors Affecting Ulnar Neuropathy**Geetha Rani B.G.¹, Shri Hari B.G.², Balachandra N.³**¹Associate Professor, Department of Anatomy, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar Medical College & Hospital, Shampura Main Road, K.G. Halli, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India.² Assistant Professor, Department of Neurosurgery, Bangalore Medical College and Research Institute, Krishna Rajendra Road, Kalasipalya, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India.³Professor & HOD, Department of Anatomy, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar Medical College & Hospital, Shampura Main Road, K.G. Halli, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India.

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Abstract:**Objective:** To review the anatomical features of conventional sites of compression of ulnar nerve & discuss the probable influence on ulnar neuropathy.**Methods:** Total of 67 embalmed cadaveric upper limbs were studied in Dr. B.R. Ambedkar Medical College, Bengaluru, for the course of ulnar nerve in upper limb. special attentions were given to its course in arm underneath struthers arcade, at elbow in cubital tunnel& at hand in guyons canal.**Results:** Struthers arcade showed a 100% incidence, among which 86.7% is thickened form of intermuscular septum, 19.2% was ligamentous at its distal end (internal brachial ligament). Osborne's ligament continued from medial epicondyle to olecranon process to also connecting between FCU heads (62%), between FCU & FDP (22%), between FCU & PT (16%). The cubital tunnel roof was also reinforced by anconeus epitrochlear is in (17%) specimen.**Conclusion:** The different anatomical variants of these conventional sites of compression should be kept in mind which would help in the diagnostic & prognostic recovery of ulnar neuropathy.**Keywords:** Ulnar Neuropathy, Struthers Arcade, Cubital Tunnel, Guyons Canal.

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Introduction

The ulnar nerve also called the Musicians nerve of hand [1], is a mixed nerve with a principal role in movements of hand as it innervates the vast majority of the intrinsic hand muscles. It is one of the most clinically relevant nerves of the upper limb, due to its superficial course and clinically discernible role in agile movements of hand[2]. The ulnar nerve innervates the flexor muscles of the forearm including the flexor carpi ulnaris and flexor digitorum profundus, thereby causing flexion and adduction of wrist. ulnar nerve also innervates, adductor pollicis and medial head of the flexor pollicis brevis controlling movement of fifth digit[1,2]. Due to this function we are able to manipulate work with tools, instruments and play a role in fine movements like pinching, gripping seen in daily activities. In the hand, its superficial branch provides sensory innervation to medial one and half hand while Deep branch innervates hypothenar muscles, lumbricals, dorsal & palmar interossei muscles, thereby causing finger adduction, abduction, flexion at the respective metacarpophalangeal (MCP) joint and extension at the proximal interphalangeal (PIP) and distal interphalangeal (DIP) joints. This position of hand is

important in writing, sewing, stitching, eating, stringing, buttoning etc. ulnar neuropathy is the second most common entrapment neuropathy following that of median nerve.[2,3]

From being branch of brachial plexus, ulnar nerve courses along medial part of the arm from the anterior to the posterior compartment, through the medial intermuscular septum, called the arcade of Struthers. The arcade is formed by the medial head of Biceps, medial intermuscular septum, and internal Brachial ligament. It then runs to lie behind the medial epicondyle of the humerus. At the distal elbow, the ulnar nerve enters the cubital tunnel underneath Osborne's ligament (retinaculum between the two heads of the flexor carpi ulnaris muscle). It continues through the flexor and pronator muscles of the forearm and into the wrist, superficial to the flexor retinaculum. The ulnar nerve enters the hand through the Guyon's canal, a fibro-osseous tunnel formed by the pisiform and hook of Hamate. In the hand, the ulnar nerve branches to give rise to superficial cutaneous branch & a deep motor branch. the superficial branch providing sensation to the hand and deep motor branch takes a lateral turn

around hook of Hamate widely branching to supply intrinsic muscles of hand[1].

Ulnar nerve injury can be caused by reasons based on location of injury along its course. cubital tunnel syndrome is the second most common neuropathy after carpal tunnel syndrome. The conventional sites of ulnar neuropathy are struthers arcade, cubital tunnel & Guyons canal [2,3]. ulnar nerve compression in struthers arcade or at the elbow may result in cubital tunnel syndrome, and compression at Guyon's canal of the wrist can manifest as Guyons canal/ulnar tunnel syndrome[4]. The reasons for compression could be prolonged periods of elbow flexion like sleep, exercise, driving, typing, or talking on phone. Intrinsic factors like anatomical variants around these regions are important to be identified to promptly and correctly diagnose nerve dysfunction to prevent delay of treatment or recurrence of symptoms. Though the incidence of ulnar neuropathy is not precisely documented, it has seen an emerging trend with most of them working on desktop/computer related jobs where in there is a prolonged stretching, direct pressure on nerve with elbow fully bent or leaning elbow(hence pressure on cubital tunnel, struthers arcade)/hand (Guyons canal) against a solid surface[5,6]. As previous studies are focussed on incidences of the conventional sites of compression, we intended to study the anatomical nature of these structures & also look for additional sites around ulnar nerve that could cause compression.

Materials & Methods

The study was conducted in Dr. B.R. Ambedkar Medical College, Bengaluru, Department of Anatomy. 67 formalin embalmed unpaired upper limbs of either sex were dissected ranging in age from 50 to 70 years. None of these cadavers had a history or anatomical evidence of ulnar neuropathy. All elbows were within the anatomical limits of normal cubital angles [5 to 30 valgus) no pathology or past surgical incisions were noted in the areas dissected and no specimen had a known ulnar nerve pathology. According to Cunningham's manual of human dissection. the ulnar nerve was dissected in the upper limb. We delineated the boundaries of struthers arcade, cubital tunnel & guyons canal.

Observations of the fascial relationships of the ulnar nerve in the forearm were recorded.

Results

Arcade of struthers was present in 100% of all limbs dissected. 58/67 (86.7%) formation was due to thickened medial intermuscular septum (mean length 7.58cm). 12/67 (19.2%) was due to internal brachial ligament (thickened distal medial intermuscular septum). Osborne's ligament formed the roof of the tunnel in all the elbows dissected between medial epicondyle & olecranon. it

continued with aponeurosis between humeral & ulnar head of FCU -41/67(62.5%), between FCU & FDP -15/67(22.3%), between FCU & PRONATOR TERES 11/67(16.4%). Anatomical features of Osborne's ligament-thin membranous in 40/67(59.7%), thick fibrous in 22/67(32.8%). Roof of cubital tunnel was reinforced by anconeus epitrochlear is in 12/67(17.9%) where in it was extension of anconeus in 7/67(10.44%), triceps brachii in 5/67(7.4%). The tunnel floor made of medial collateral ligament & elbow joint capsule showed no considerable variations. Guyons canal showed an average length of 42mm. At proximal pisiform level it was wider & at hook of hamate level it was narrower. Distal part of tunnel was narrower because of FDM attachment with pisiform bone & hook of hamate connected by musculotendinous arch-the pisohamate hiatus. This arch was thin muscular in 26/67 (42.7%), Musculo fibrous in 16/67 (27.1%), musculoligamentous in 27/67 (35.1%).

Discussion

History, etymology, & epidemiology: In actual fact, struthers arcade was identified by kane in 1973 but he named it after struthers. It was in 1957 [7], Geoffrey Vaughan Osborne called attention to a fibrous band connecting the humeral & ulnar head of flexor carpi ulnaris and named it as Osborne ligament, which is now also known as arcuate ligament, cubital tunnel retinaculum, Osbornes fascia, tendinous arch [8,9]. Odriscoll referred it to as cubital tunnel retinaculum and inferred it as a remainder of epitrochlear is, Dellon et al termed it as an evolutionarily advanced Anconeusepitrochlearis, vanderpool said that if present it replaces Osbornes ligament.

In 1861 the French anatomist & surgeon Jean Casimir Guyon (also known as father of modern urology) described the anatomy of this region. Later in 1965 -Dupont et al coined the term ulnar tunnel syndrome for symptoms produced by compressed ulnar nerve running in this space [10]. Panas as early as in 1878 described traumatic ulnar nerve dysfunction, while hunt described spontaneous nerve dysfunction in as early as 1900's.

Arcade of Struthers

In recent times, ochiai et al reported entrapment of ulnar nerve in struthers arcade, while some authors have even implicated the structure in failed cubital tunnel surgery.

Amadio et al(100%), Al-qattan& murray (68%) (10), Gonzalez(67%) [11] reported varying incident rate of arcade of struthers, however Dellon, Bartels, won et, laurent wehrli et al [12,13] did not encounter the structure in which unar nerve travelled from arm to elbow, even suggesting to cancel the concept of struthers arcade. Apart from the varying rate of incidences, there were controversy even in describing

the structure of struthers arcade

Our aim of the study was to further elucidate the anatomy of struthers arcade in Indian population. We identified that struthers arcade was found consistently in 100% of cases. Among them 86.7% was due to thick brachial fascia, 19.2% was thickened distally due to internal brachial ligament. Based on our findings we can anatomically conclude that in

majority, arcade of struthers is an anatomical band of thickened fascial condensation of medial intermuscular septum with Ulnar nerve being freely mobile inside it which implies ulnar nerve is less prone for compression, whereas, if this medial intermuscular septum becomes thickened in distal segment and connects with medial head of triceps as internal brachial ligament, then in such cases it might be vulnerable for compression.

Osborne ligament

Dellon et al 77% [11], James et al 91% [13], Karatas 8% [14], Gonzalez 100% [15] were the reported incidences of Osborne ligament in cubital tunnel. Machi et al described that the Osborne ligament formed the roof of cubital tunnel and it was trilaminarfascio-tendinio-muscular structure.

Waugh, Grenata reported that the cubital tunnel volume reduced deep to the ligament during elbow flexion, thus contributing to cubital tunnel syndrome." driscoll [14] classified its morphology, referred it to as cubital tunnel retinaculum and considered it as remainder of epitrochlearis,

similarly Dellon et al described it as evolutionarily enhanced version of anconeus epitrochlearis, vanderpool even added that when this muscle is present it replaces Osborne's ligament.

Conventionally the medial epicondyle and olecranon considered to be the walls on either side of the tunnel but it can be seen from our study that cubital tunnel very well extends beyond these bony landmarks with Osborne's ligament extending furthermore into the fibro muscular walls between flexor carpi ulnaris & flexor digitorum profundus (38/67)/superficialis (11/67)/pronator teres (5/67). This suggests that in the extended concept of cubital

tunnel, it is the nerve between the aponeurosis of flexor carpi ulnaris & flexor digitorum profundus & other flexor muscles -which are with a narrower space & more prone for compression than between the medial condyle and olecranon process. Posner (compressive neuropathy) recounted that medial epicondylectomies were effective in only in 50% cases & they had the highest recurrence rate & recommended that the distal areas especially the aponeurotic margin covering the flexor muscles need to be probed in cases of cubital tunnel syndrome to stave off its incomplete treatment or its recurrences.

Guyons canal

Though the true incidence & prevalence of Guyons canal syndrome is not documented, it is being increasingly reported in neurology out patients especially in patients with desk job having to put more pressure in medial half of palm (i.e., Guyons canal) while working on computer system. It is also seen in sports persons who play sports with a club /racquet or long-distance cyclers/manual labourers requiring constant pressure on the wrist. This illustrative study on Guyon canal revealed consistent boundaries as mentioned in previous literature, but also reveals variations in the distal component –the pisohamate hiatus.

The perception of shape of Guyons canal kept changing from initially described rounded canal (Guyon) [16], to a tunnel (Grantham- as it has a learning roof) [17,18,19]. Shea & McClain [20] (1969), Gross & Gilberman (1985) gave a more appropriate description of compressive zone in ulnar tunnel.

Our study revealed that Guyons canal had triangular cross section. It was wider in proximal pisiform level & being narrowest at level of hook of hamate. Vanderpools concept of pisohamate hiatus was reaffirmed in our findings in distal part of Guyons canal. We also observed that attachment between pisiform bone & hook of hamate was buttressed by flexor digiti minimi extensions which were thin muscular (35/62-56%), musculoligamentous (7/62-11%). The deep motor branch passed beneath this structure while turning radially around the hook of hamate, hence we concluded that the fibrous /ligamentous nature of these extensions along with pressure on this region would affect the compression of ulnar nerve. However we could not establish the bilaterality as the study was done in unpaired hands. Ignacio uriburu stressed that after [21,22] exploring Guyons canal, pisohamate hiatus has to be widened to treat patient with wrist pain, progressive weakness & muscle wasting of ulnar hand.[23,24] Our findings also agree with uriburu suggesting a need to explore distal Guyons /pisohamate hiatus as this seemed a narrow zone than distance between pisiform and hamate bone (unlike conventional

description).

Conclusion

Thus as more anatomical features on Struthers arcade, flexor extensions around cubital tunnel & distal zone of Guyons canal (pisohamate hiatus) are being revealed, this knowledge may be helpful in taking into account for management of ulnar neuropathy.

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